

Beak measurements of the Atlantic bobtail squid *Sepioloatlantica* (Cephalopoda: Sepiolidae): appropriate predictors of its body size and weight

Dimensiones de las mandíbulas de la sepiola del Atlántico *Sepioloatlantica* (Cephalopoda: Sepiolidae): indicadores apropiados de su tamaño y peso

Marcelo RODRIGUES*, Jesús S. TRONCOSO* and Ángel GUERRA**

Recibido el 22-X-2012. Aceptado el 19-XII-2012

ABSTRACT

This work provides the relationships between nine mandible (beak) measurements and dorsal mantle length (ML), body mass (BW) and sex of 101 specimens (22 juveniles, 35 females, 44 males) of the Atlantic bobtail squid *Sepioloatlantica* from the Ría de Vigo (Galician waters, NW Spain). No significant differences were found between male and female beak measurements with discriminant analysis. Using linear regression analysis for grouped males and females it was found that some parts of the beaks grew isometrically whereas others grew asymmetrically. Likely reasons of these discrepancies are discussed. It was shown that lower rostral length and upper rostral length were the parameters that best predict ML and/or BW of *S. atlantica* when using the full dataset (juveniles + males + females).

RESUMEN

Este trabajo proporciona las relaciones entre nueve medidas de las mandíbulas (picos) y la longitud dorsal del manto (ML), masa corporal (BW) y sexo de 101 especímenes (22 juveniles, 35 hembras y 44 machos) del sepiólido *Sepioloatlantica* provenientes de la Ría de Vigo (Galicia, NO de España). No se detectaron diferencias significativas entre las dimensiones del pico de machos y hembras mediante análisis discriminante. Al utilizar regresiones lineales para analizar machos y hembras conjuntamente se verificó que unas partes de los picos crecieron isométricamente mientras otras alométricamente. Se discuten los posibles motivos de estas discrepancias. Se demostró que longitud rostral de la mandíbula inferior y la longitud del rostro de la superior son los parámetros que mejor predicen la ML o la BW de *S. atlantica* cuando se utilizó el conjunto de datos completo (juveniles + machos + hembras).

INTRODUCTION

The members of the family Sepiolidae, commonly known as bobtail squids, are represented in tropical, temperate and sub polar waters of all oceans (REID

AND JEREB, 2005). The Atlantic bobtail squid *Sepioloatlantica* d'ORBIGNY, 1840 is widely distributed in the North-eastern Atlantic from latitudes 65°N to 35°N

* Departamento de Ecología y Biología Animal. Facultad de Ciencias del Mar. Campus Lagoas Marcosende, 36310. Universidade de Vigo. Vigo. Spain. marcelorodrigues@uvigo.es

** Instituto de Investigaciones Marinas (CSIC). Eduardo Cabello 6, 36208 Vigo. Spain.

(REID AND JEREB, 2005), and it is a nekto-benthic relatively abundant species along its range of distribution (JONES AND RICHARDSON, 2012; RODRIGUES, GARCÍ, TRONCOSO AND GUERRA, 2011A).

S. atlantica plays a role as both prey and predator in marine ecosystems. As prey it has been found in the stomach contents of several cephalopod species (CASTRO AND GUERRA, 1990; BLANC, PINCZON DU SEL AND DAGUZAN, 1998), fish (PATTERSON, 1985; VELASCO, OLASO AND SÁNCHEZ, 2001; MAHE, AMARA, BRYCKAERT, KACHER AND BRYLINSKI, 2007) and top predators like marine mammals (SILVA, 1999; PIERREPONT, DUBOIS AND DESORMONTS, 2005). As predator, *S. atlantica* eats small fish (RODRIGUES, TRONCOSO, GARCÍ AND GUERRA, 2011B), mysid shrimp (YAU AND BOYLE, 1996; JONES AND RICHARDSON, 2010; RODRIGUES ET AL., 2011B; RODRIGUES, GUERRA AND TRONCOSO, 2011C) and amphipods (YAU AND BOYLE, 1996). Cephalopod mandibles or "beaks" are hard structures composed of chitin-protein complexes (HUNT AND NIXON, 1981), which resist digestion, and can accumulate in the stomachs of predators (CLARKE, 1986). Cephalopod beak morphometry is a useful tool for taxonomy (Clarke, 1962; 1986; PÉREZ-GÁNDARAS, 1983). Some parameters of these structures show accurate relationship with size and body mass of the animal and can also be used for estimating the size of consumed cephalopods as well as assessing trophic interactions and predator-prey relations (CLARKE, 1996; BELLO, 1996; STAUDINGER, JUANES AND CARLSON, 2009; PETRIĆ, FERRI, ŠKELJO AND KRUSTULOVIĆ ŠIFNER, 2010). This is essential for biomass calculations (PÉREZ-GÁNDARAS, 1983; CLARKE, 1986; 1987).

Although the beak morphology has been described for *S. atlantica* (PÉREZ-GÁNDARAS 1983, GUERRA 1986), this work aims to provide a better understanding of the relationship between beak measurements, body size, body mass and sex using a complete dataset, which comprises a wide size range and all the maturity stages of the species.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A total of 101 specimens (22 juveniles, 35 females, 44 males) have been examined. Samples were obtained in several dives carried out in the Ría of Vigo (42°14' N; 8°47' W - NW Iberian Peninsula) between November 2007 and December 2009. Depth of collection ranged from 4 to 8 meters. The seabed was sandy, without seaweed, and with presence of ripplemarks.

Living bobtail squids were transported to the Marine Station of the University of Vigo at Toralla Island (ECIMAT) where the current study was mainly undertaken. In the laboratory, all specimens were anesthetized in a 1:1 mixture of artificial sea water and 7.14% MgCl₂ (MESSENGER, 1985). Dorsal mantle length (ML), and body mass (BW) were immediately measured to 0.001 mm and 0.01 g accuracy, respectively. Specimens were also sexed following RODRIGUES, GUERRA AND TRONCOSO (2012). Beaks were carefully removed and analysed within 0.001 mm accuracy under a Nikon SMZ-1500 stereomicroscope directly connected to a computer with image analysis software (Nikon, NIS-Elements, Tokyo, Japan). All beak measurements were made on preserved (70% ethanol) specimens. Four measurements from the upper beaks (UB) and five from lower beaks (LB) for all males and females were obtained according to the nomenclature of CLARKE (1962, 1986) and PÉREZ-GÁNDARAS (1983) (Figure 1). Measurements recorded from UB were: upper rostral length (URL), upper hood length (UHL), upper crest length (UCL), and upper hood height (UHH). For the LB the following measurements were recorded: lower rostral length (LRL), lower hood length (LHL), lower crest length (LCL), lower hood height (LHH) and lower baseline length (LBL). In juveniles, only URL and LRL were measured, because beaks were very soft and broke easily.

Relationships between each beak measurement and the corresponding individual ML or BW were calculated using linear regressions. All data were

Figure 1. Beak measurements for *Sepiola atlantica*. A. Upper beak: upper rostral length (URL), upper hood length (UHL), upper crest length (UCL), and upper hood height (UHH); B. Lower beak: lower rostral length (LRL), lower hood length (LHL), lower crest length (LCL), lower hood height (LHH) and lower baseline length (LBL).

Figura 1. Medidas de las mandíbulas de *Sepiola atlantica*. A. Mandíbula superior: longitud rostral superior (URL), longitud del capuchón superior (UHL), longitud de la cresta superior (UCL), y altura del capuchón superior (UHH); B. Mandíbula inferior: longitud rostral inferior (LRL), longitud del capuchón inferior (LHL), longitud de la cresta inferior (LCL), altura del capuchón inferior (LHH), y longitud de la línea base del pico inferior (LBL).

previously transformed using decimal logarithms (ln). This analysis allowed calculating the relative growth rate ("b") using minimum squares (RICKER, 1973). Values of $b > 1$ indicate positive allometry, $b < 1$ negative allometry, and $b = 1$ isometry in the length-length relationships. Isometric growth is expressed for $b = 3$ in the length-weight relationships (RICKER, 1973). To verify whether UB and LB differ between sexes, a discriminate analysis was carried out using all morphological variables for sexed specimens. All analyses were undertaken with the IBM SPSS® 19 Statistics package.

RESULTS

The 101 measured specimens of *Sepiola atlantica* fall within the three ML classes that covered a wide size range and all maturity stages of this species. ML ranges for each class are shown in

Table I. Upper and lower beak morphology coincides with the one described by CLARKE (1962; 1980) for members of the family Sepiolidae, and matches the characters provided by PÉREZ-GÁNDARAS (1983) for *S. atlantica* specimens.

Ratios and main characteristics for lower and upper beaks of the species are as follows:

Lower beak (LB)

$LRL \leq 0.7$ mm; Ratios: $LCL/LHL=2.09$; $LHL/LRL=1.61$; $LRL/LWL=0.72$; $LCL/LWL=2.29$, where LCL: lower crest length; LHL: lower hood length; LRL: lower rostral length; LWL: lower wing length. Other characteristics: i) the lower beak lacks rostral hood; ii) the distance between the crest and the hood is moderate; III) the crest profile is slightly curved; iv) the wing has no lateral fold; v) the posterior and external border of the hood present a broad and shallow recess; vi) the hood surface is smooth; vii) the external border of the wing is

Table I. *Sepiola atlantica*. Range of measurements (minimum - maximum) for each studied class. BW: Body weight (g), ML: dorsal mantle length (mm), URL: upper rostral length (mm), UHL: upper hood length (mm), UCL: upper crest length (mm), UHH: upper hood height (mm), LHL: lower hood length (mm), LRL: lower rostral length, LCL: lower crest length (mm), LHH: lower hood height (mm), LBL: lower baseline length (mm).

Tabla I. *Sepiola atlantica*. Rango de medidas (mínimo - máximo) en cada clase estudiada. BW: peso corporal (g), ML: longitud dorsal del manto (mm), URL: longitud rostral superior (mm), UHL: longitud del capuchón superior (mm), UCL: longitud de la cresta superior (mm), UHH: altura del capuchón superior (mm), LRL: longitud rostral inferior (mm), LHL: longitud del capuchón inferior (mm), LCL: longitud de la cresta inferior (mm), LHH: altura del capuchón inferior (mm), LBL: longitud de la línea base del pico inferior (mm).

Class	n	ML	BW	URL	UHL	UCL
Juveniles	22	2.70-4.63	0.01-0.11	0.14-0.34	-	-
Females	35	4.22-18.31	0.08-2.39	0.21-0.69	1.05-2.33	1.21-4.23
Males	44	3.87-14.44	0.05-1.97	0.28-0.71	0.92-2.10	1.82-3.92
Class	UHH	LRL	LHL	LCL	LHH	LBL
Juveniles	-	0.07-0.33	-	-	-	-
Females	0.85-2.86	0.22-0.71	0.33-1.11	0.84-2.31	0.66-2.49	0.80-2.35
Males	0.47-2.41	0.19-0.54	0.39-1.03	1.01-1.96	0.75-1.93	0.97-2.05

Table II. *Sepiola atlantica*. Discriminant analysis for sex effect on the upper and lower beak measurements.

Tabla II. *Sepiola atlantica*. Análisis discriminante entre el sexo y las medidas de las mandíbulas superior e inferior.

Sample	Variables	Effect	Wilks'lambda	df 1	df 2	p
Both sexes	Upper Beak	1	0.74	4	79	0.056
Both sexes	Lower Beak	1	0.86	5	79	0.102

low, barely concealing the mandible angle profile; viii) the shoulder forms a long crest with an intermediate cartilaginous layer present; ix) wing with radiate streaks from the shoulder; and x) rostral border formed as a jagged thin sheet.

Upper beak

Ratios: UCL/UHL=1.80; UHL/URL=3.58; URL/UWL=0.64; UCL/UWL=4.33; where UCL: upper crest length; UHL: upper hood length; URL: upper rostral length; UWL: upper wing length. Other characteristics: i) the distance between the crest and the hood is very short; ii) the palate has two small lateral grooves,

no ribs; iii) the mandible angle is almost 90°; and iv) rostral border is formed as a jagged thin sheet.

Results of the discriminant analysis showed that UB and LB characteristics were not significantly different between males and females (Table II). This analysis also showed that UB and LB growth depends only on ML and BW. Since no significant differences were detected between sexes, both sexes were considered together for further analysis.

Linear computed regressions for grouped males and females revealed a significant relationship ($p < 0.001$) between all beak measurements and ML or BW. However, the relationship

Table III. *Sepiolo atlantica*. Linear regression equations between the dorsal mantle length (ML) or body mass (BW) and beak measurements for grouped male and female individuals. LRL: lower rostral length, LHL: lower hood length, LCL: lower crest length, LHH: lower hood height, LBL: lower baseline length, URL: upper rostral length, UHL: upper hood length, UCL: upper crest length, UHH: upper hood height.

Tabla III. *Sepiolo atlantica*. Regresión lineal entre la longitud dorsal del manto (ML), o la masa corporal (BW), y medidas de las mandíbulas para machos y hembras agrupados. LRL: longitud rostral inferior, LHL: longitud del capuchón inferior, LCL: longitud de la cresta inferior, LHH: altura del capuchón inferior, LBL: longitud de la línea base del pico inferior, URL: longitud rostral superior, UHL: longitud del capuchón superior, UCL: longitud de la cresta superior, UHH: altura del capuchón superior.

Regression equations	n	Regression coefficient	Standard error (b)	r ²	F	p
<i>Lower beak</i>						
Ln BW = 1.486 + 2.147 LnLRL	79	0.73	0.23	0.53	88.14	0.001
Ln BW = 0.525 + 2.568 LnLHL	79	0.81	0.21	0.66	148.94	0.001
Ln BW = -1.762 + 3.074 LnLCL	79	0.84	0.23	0.70	181.76	0.001
Ln BW = -1.209 + 1.990 LnLBL	79	0.65	0.27	0.42	56.17	0.001
Ln BW = -1.723 + 2.937 LnLHH	79	0.84	0.22	0.71	183.97	0.001
Ln ML = 3.173 + 0.974 LnLRL	79	0.73	0.11	0.53	86.86	0.001
Ln ML = 2.744 + 1.183 LnLHL	79	0.82	0.09	0.68	159.69	0.001
Ln ML = 1.700 + 1.392 LnLCL	79	0.83	0.11	0.70	175.48	0.001
Ln ML = 1.945 + 0.919 LnLBL	79	0.66	0.12	0.43	59.07	0.001
Ln ML = 1.334 + 1.716 LnLHH	79	0.84	0.10	0.70	181.39	0.001
<i>Upper beak</i>						
Ln BW = 1.590 + 2.734 LnURL	79	0.81	0.23	0.66	146.68	0.001
Ln BW = -1.725 + 2.979 LnUHL	79	0.78	0.27	0.61	121.68	0.001
Ln BW = -3.167 + 2.618 LnUCL	79	0.75	0.26	0.57	100.74	0.001
Ln BW = -1.515 + 1.961 LnUHH	79	0.72	0.22	0.51	81.22	0.001
Ln ML = 1.223 + 3.206 LnURL	79	0.80	0.11	0.63	132.97	0.001
Ln ML = 1.708 + 1.371 LnUHL	79	0.79	0.12	0.63	128.83	0.001
Ln ML = 1.038 + 1.211 LnUCL	79	0.77	0.12	0.59	108.67	0.001
Ln ML = 1.788 + 0.937 LnUHH	79	0.75	0.09	0.57	100.25	0.001

between BW and Lower Baseline Length (Table III) showed the lowest coefficient of correlation ($r^2 < 50\%$). The best LB measurement predictor to BW and ML was the Lower Hood Height, while in the UB it was the Upper Rostral Length for both ML and BW (Table III).

The equations shown in Table III display different relationships between variables. The shape of the LB showed a practically isometric growth in relation to BW, this is the case of the Lower Crest Length and the Lower Hood Height; however it was weakly isometric or negative allometric for Lower Rostral Length and Lower Hood Length. In the case of LBL *vs* BW a clear negative allo-

metric was found. All UB measures, except Upper Hood Height -that was negative allometric-, showed a weak negative allometric growth.

Regressions between the nine beak variables *vs* ML showed isometric growth except of LRL, LBL and UHH, although they were very close to an isometric growth pattern. On the other hand, LHH was the beak variable that shows faster growing when fitted against ML. Alternatively, URL was the faster growing UB parameter in respect to ML (Table III).

When all specimens (juveniles + males + females) were pooled together, URL_{all} and LRL_{all} showed a significant

Table IV. *Sepiolo atlantica*. Linear regression equations between the dorsal mantle length (ML) or body mass (BW) and two beak measurements for grouped juvenile, male and female individuals. LRL: lower rostral length, and URL: upper rostral length.

Tabla IV. *Sepiolo atlantica*. Regresiones lineales entre la longitud dorsal del manto (ML), o la masa corporal (BW), y dos medidas de las mandíbulas para juveniles, machos y hembras agrupados. LRL: longitud rostral inferior, y URL: longitud rostral superior.

Regression equations	n	Regression coefficient	Standard error (b)	r ²	F	p
<i>Lower beak</i>						
Ln BW = 1.404 + 2.108 LnLRLall	101	0.86	0.13	0.74	285.94	0.001
Ln ML = 3.060 + 0.865 LnLRLall	101	0.86	0.05	0.73	271.44	0.001
<i>Upper beak</i>						
Ln BW = 2.034 + 3.448 LnURLall	101	0.88	0.19	0.78	343.93	0.001
Ln ML = 3.324 + 1.422 LnURLall	101	0.88	0.08	0.77	337.02	0.001

relationship with both ML and BW ($p < 0.001$) with higher regression coefficient score (Table IV) than the ones computed for males and females together (Table III). The relationships between URL_{all} and BW or ML explained up to 78% (r^2) and were positively allometric. Otherwise, LRL_{all} showed negative allometry when plotted against both ML and BW.

DISCUSSION

The studies carried out with *S. atlantica* from the Ría de Vigo have provided new insights on several aspects of its life cycle and ecology (see RODRIGUES ET AL., 2012; 2011A; B; C). With whole-body and fresh specimens provided by sampling dives during these studies it was easy to identify the species using previous works (e.g. GUERRA, 1986; BELLO, 1995; DE HEIJ AND GOUD, 2010). However, it is actually difficult to distinguish between the different *Sepiolo* species only from their beaks (PÉREZ-GÁNDARAS, 1983; CLARKE, 1980). In the case of wanting to identify species from the stomach content of any of their potential predators, beside size and characteristics of the beaks, the geographical distribution of the species in question as well as of the predator are both helpful hints (CLARKE 1980). The

shape and measurements given herein for beaks of *S. atlantica* agree with those provided by GUERRA (1986) and PÉREZ-GÁNDARAS (1983). They are also quite similar to other bobtail squids (PÉREZ-GÁNDARAS, 1983; LU AND ICKERINGIL, 2002; AÇIK AND SALMAN, 2010). Our result that there is no significant difference between beak morphology of males and females of *S. atlantica* also agree with previous analysis by PÉREZ-GÁNDARAS (1983) for the same species in Galician waters (NW Spain).

Growth rates of cephalopods, including hard structures, can be strongly influenced by environmental changes, as well as by availability and type of food (PIERCE ET AL., 2008). Considering that we analysed a *S. atlantica* population within a small and uniform ecosystem, the absence of differences in beak shape could be due to exposure to the same abiotic and biotic conditions. However, these morphometric analyses using beak measurements could be different if they were undertaken with specimens covering the whole range of distribution of the species. Thus, geographic intraspecific variations were found in other species (BOYLE AND NGOILE, 1993; PIERCE ET AL., 1994; ROCHA AND GUERRA, 1999; PETRIC ET AL., 2010), and between seasonal spawning groups (KASHIWADA, RECKSIEK AND KARPOV, 1979), as well as intraspecific

variation due to growth and sexual dimorphism (BELLO, 2001).

Beak biometric relationships have been examined in species of the three Sepiolidae subfamilies (Sepiolinae, Rossinae and Heteroteuthinae) showing that they are a good predictor of ML and BW (PÉREZ-GÁNDARAS, 1983; CLARKE, 1986; LU AND ICKERINGIL, 2002; AÇIK AND SALMAN, 2010). Unfortunately, the data available in the literature for relationships between beak parameters and ML were obtained without log transformed measurements, which precludes suitable comparisons with our results. However, the aforementioned works provided comparisons between beak parameters and BW using log transformed data. The slopes of the equations obtained for BW were similar those obtained for *S. atlantica* in the present paper. Allometric conditions were discrepant when comparing male and female variables, as is the case of BW and/or ML vs URL (Table III) showing a negative and positive allometry condition, respectively. Alternatively, when using our full dataset that covers the five maturity stages proposed for *S. atlantica* (RODRIGUES ET AL., 2012) the agreement of allometry conditions between ML and BW was obtained (Table IV). The implications of this interaction are difficult to resolve since sex was found to have no significant effect by itself. In consequence, factors other than body size, weight or sex have major effects on the beak's growth during the lifetime of *S. atlantica*, and one of these factors might be sexual maturation, as shown by KASHIWADA ET AL. (1979) in the

squid *Loligo opalescens* and STAUDINGER ET AL. (2009) for *Loligo pealeii* and *Illex illecebrosus*. Nevertheless, it must be born in mind that some of the allometry found could be due to the inaccuracy of the beak parameter measurements. In this regard, the LHH and UHH (Fig. 1) can be very inaccurately measured due to beak deformations.

The results presented here are the most comprehensive dataset on the shape and morphometrics of *S. atlantica* beaks to date. The present data can successfully be used as a predictor of ML and/or BW of the species, especially LRL_{all} and URL_{all} (Table IV). Since quantification of predator-prey body size relationships are crucial to understand trophic dynamics in marine ecosystems, the results of the present study are intended to help quantitative assessments of *S. atlantica* prey in the diets of its predators.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are very grateful to Cristian Aldea (CEQUA - Chile) for his valuable help with the software used in this manuscript. We also would like to thank Fernando Aneiros, Patricia Esquete-Garrote (ADAM - UVIGO) and Álvaro Roura (ECOBIO MAR - IIM, CSIC) for the discussions, which were very useful to improve this manuscript. The first author was supported by a scholarship from the *Consellería de Educación e Ordenación Universitaria da Xunta de Galicia*.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- AÇIK S. AND SALMAN A. 2010. Estimation of body size from the beaks of eight sepiolid species (Cephalopoda: Sepiolidae) from the Eastern Mediterranean Sea. *Molluscan Research*, 30: 154-164.
- BELLO G. 1995. A key for the identification of the Mediterranean sepiolids (Mollusca: Cephalopoda). *Bulletin de l'Institut Océanographique* (Monaco), 16: 41-56.
- BELLO G. 1996. Teuthophagous predators as collectors of oceanic cephalopods: the case of the Adriatic Sea. *Bollettino Malacologico*, 32: 71-78.
- BELLO G. 2001. Dimorphic growth in male and female cuttlefish *Sepia orbignyana* (Cephalopoda: Sepiidae) from the Adriatic Sea. *Helgoland Marine Research*, 55: 124-127.

- BLANC A., PINCZON DU SEL G. AND DAGUZAN J. 1998. Habitat and diet of early stages of *Sepia officinalis* L. (Cephalopoda) in Morbihan Bay. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 64: 263-274.
- BOYLE P. R. AND NGOILE M.A.K. 1993. Population variation and growth in *Loligo forbesi* (Cephalopoda: Loliginidae) from Scottish waters. In Okutani, T., O'Dor, R. K. and Kubodera T (Ed.): *Recent advances in cephalopod fisheries biology*. Tokai University Press, Tokyo: 49-59.
- CASTRO B.G. AND GUERRA Á. 1990. The diet of *Sepia officinalis* and *Sepia elegans* (Cephalopoda, Sepioidea) from the Ria de Vigo. *Scientia Marina*, 54: 375-388.
- CLARKE M.R. 1962. The identification of cephalopod "beaks" and the relationship between size and total body weight. *Bulletin of the British Museum (Natural History) Zoology*, 8: 419-480.
- CLARKE M.R. 1980. Cephalopods in the diet of sperm whales of the southern hemisphere and their bearing on sperm whale biology. *Discovery Reports*, 37, 324 pp.
- CLARKE M.R. 1986. A handbook for identification of cephalopod beaks. Clarendon, Oxford, 273 pp.
- CLARKE M. R. 1987. Cephalopod biomass. Estimations from predation. In Boyle, P. R. (Ed.): *Cephalopod Life Cycles*. Vol. II. Comparative Reviews. Academic Press, London, 221-237.
- CLARKE M.R. 1996. Cephalopod as prey. III. Cetaceans. In Clarke, M.R. (Ed.): *The role of cephalopods in the world's oceans*. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London, Series B*. 351: 1053-1065.
- DE HEIJ A. AND GOUD J. 2010. *Sepiola tridens* spec. nov., an overlooked species (Cephalopoda, Sepiolidae) living in the North Sea and north-eastern Atlantic Ocean. *Basteria*, 74: 51-62.
- GUERRA A. 1986. Sepiolinae (Mollusca, Cephalopoda) de la Ría de Vigo. *Iberus*, 6: 175-184.
- HUNT S. AND NIXON M. 1981. A comparative study of protein composition in the chitin-protein complexes of the beak, pen, sucker disc, radula and oesophageal cuticle of cephalopods. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology*, 68B: 535-546.
- JONES N.J.E. AND RICHARDSON C.A. 2010. Laboratory culture, growth, and the life cycle of the little cuttlefish *Sepiola atlantica* (Cephalopoda: Sepiolidae). *Journal of Shellfish Research*, 29: 241-246.
- JONES N.J.E. AND RICHARDSON C.A. 2012. Distribution and reproductive biology of the little cuttlefish *Sepiola atlantica* (Cephalopoda: Sepiolidae) around Anglesey, North Wales. *Helgoland Marine Research*, 66: 233-242.
- KASHIWADA J., RECKSIEK C.W. AND KARPOV K.A. 1979. Beaks of the market squid, *Loligo opalescens*, as tools for predator studies. *California Cooperative Oceanic Fisheries Investigation Report*, 20: 65-69.
- LU C.C. AND ICKERINGILL R. 2002. Cephalopod beak identification and biomass estimation techniques: tools for dietary studies of southern Australian finfishes. *Museum Victoria Science Reports*, 6: 1-65.
- MAHE K., AMARA R., BRYCKAERT T., KACHER M. AND BRYLINSKI J.M. 2007. Ontogenic and spatial variation in the diet of hake (*Merluccius merluccius*) in the Bay of Biscay and the Celtic Sea. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 64: 1210-1219.
- MESSENGER J.B. 1985. Magnesium chloride as an anaesthetic for cephalopods. *Comparative Biochemistry & Physiology*, 82C: 203-205.
- PATTERSON K.R. 1985. The trophic ecology of whiting (*Merlangius merlangus*) in the Irish Sea and its significance to the Manx herring stock. *Journal du Conseil International pour l'Exploration de la Mer*, 42: 152-161.
- PÉREZ-GANDARAS G. 1983. Estudio de los Cefalópodos Ibéricos: Sistemática y Bionomía mediante el estudio morfométrico comparado de sus mandíbulas. Ph. D. Thesis. Universidad Complutense, Madrid.
- PETRIĆ M., FERRI J., ŠKELJO F. AND KRUSTULOVIC ŠIFNER S. 2010. Body and beak measures of *Illex coindetii* (Cephalopoda: Ommastrephidae) and their relation to growth and maturity. *Cahiers Biologie Marine*, 51: 275-287.
- PIERCE G.J., THORPE R.S., HASTIE L.C., BRIERLEY A.S., GUERRA Á., BOYLE P.R., JAMIESON R. AND AVILA P. 1994. Geographic variation in *Loligo forbesi* in the Northeast Atlantic Ocean: analysis of morphometric data and tests of causal hypotheses. *Marine Biology*, 119: 541-547.
- PIERCE G.J., VALAVANIS V. D., GUERRA Á., JEREB P., ORSI-RELINI L., BELLIDO J.M., KATARA I., PIATKOWSKI U., PEREIRA J., BALGUERIAS E., SOBRINO I., LEFKADITOU E., WANG J., SANTURTUN M., BOYLE P.R., HASTIE L.C., MACLEOD C.D., SMITH J.M., VIANA M., GONZÁLEZ A.F. AND ZUUR A.F. 2008. A review of cephalopod—environment interactions in European Seas. *Hydrobiologia*, 612: 49-70.
- PIERREPONT J. F., DUBOIS B. AND DESORMONTS S. 2005. Stomach contents of English Channel cetaceans stranded on the coast of Normandy. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 85: 1539-1546.
- REID A. AND JEREB P. 2005. Family Sepiolidae Leach, 1817. In JEREB P., ROPER C.F.E. (Eds.): *Cephalopods of the world*. An annotated and illustrated catalogue of cephalopod species known to date, vol 1(4). Chambered Nautilus and Sepioids (Nautilidae, Sepiidae, Sepiolidae, Sepiadariidae, Idiosepiidae and Spirulidae). FAO, Rome, 153-203.

- RICKER W.E. 1973. Linear regressions in fishery research. *Bulletin of the Fisheries Research Board of Canada*, 30: 409-434.
- ROCHA F. AND GUERRA Á. 1999. Age and growth of two sympatric squid *Loligo vulgaris* and *Loligo forbesi*, in Galician waters (north-west Spain). *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 79: 697-707.
- RODRIGUES M., GARCÍ M.E., TRONCOSO J.S. AND GUERRA Á. 2011a. Seasonal abundance of the Atlantic bobtail squid *Sepiolo atlantica* in Galician waters (NE Atlantic). *Marine Biology Research*, 7: 812-819.
- RODRIGUES M., TRONCOSO J.S., GARCÍ M.E. AND GUERRA Á. 2011b. Técnicas de mantenimiento y cultivo de sepiólidos (Mollusca, Cephalopoda) In ESTÉVEZ J.M.G., OLABARRIA C., PÉREZ S., ROLÁN-ALVAREZ E., ROSÓN G. (Eds.): Métodos y Técnicas en investigación marina. Tecnos, Madrid, 160-173.
- RODRIGUES M., GUERRA Á. AND TRONCOSO J.S., 2011c. The embryonic phase and its implication in the hatchling size and condition of Atlantic bobtail squid *Sepiolo atlantica*. *Helgoland Marine Research*, 65: 211-216.
- RODRIGUES M., GUERRA Á. AND TRONCOSO J.S. 2012. Reproduction of the Atlantic bobtail squid *Sepiolo atlantica* (Cephalopoda: Sepiolidae) in northwest Spain. *Invertebrate Biology*, 131: 30-39.
- SILVA M. A. 1999. Diet of common dolphins, *Delphinus delphis*, off the Portuguese continental coast. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 79: 531-540.
- STAUDINGER M.D., JUANES F. AND CARLSON S. 2009. Reconstruction of original body size and estimation of allometric relationships for the longfin inshore squid (*Loligo pealeii*) and northern shortfin squid (*Illex illecebrosus*). *Fishery Bulletin*, 107: 101-105.
- VELASCO F., OLASO I., AND SANCHEZ F. 2001. The role of cephalopods as forage for the demersal fish community in southern Bay of Biscay. *Fisheries Research*, 52: 65-77.
- YAU C. AND BOYLE P.R. 1996. Ecology of *Sepiolo atlantica* (Mollusca: Cephalopoda) in the shallow sublittoral. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association United Kingdom*, 76: 733-48.

